

Premise and Promises of a Four-Day Work Schedule for Public School Teachers in the US

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Abstract - Every aspect of our society is now evolving to respond to the demands of its stakeholders. The public school system's work schedule has also evolved. The five-day school week has been the regular schedule in the public school system for over a century (Duchscherer, 2011), but people have been interested in changing it to four days in the past decade (Hamermesh & Biddle, 2022). Most of the schools that adhere to the 4-day school week have done it to cut short the finances every school year (Duchscherer, 2011), but according to Turner et al. (2017), the shift to the four-day work schedule has improved staff's morale as well. This study aimed to describe teachers' attitude towards the four-day work schedule and provide evidence on how the new schedule impacts teachers' well-being and work morale. An online survey questionnaire was answered by 80 randomly selected participants from the Independence School District to achieve the objectives of this study. The data gathered were analyzed through mean score analysis and presented to the St. Joseph School District, which does not follow the 4-day school week. It has been found that teachers have a positive attitude towards the four-day work schedule. Also, after implementing the four-day work schedule, teachers' well-being greatly improved and their work morale was positively affected.

Keywords: Four-Day Work Schedule, Teacher Well-Being, and Teacher Work Morale

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1. Introduction

Teachers are expected to work eight hours from Monday through Friday, 180 days a year, to achieve learning goals. Teachers engage with students, work on assessments, and provide proper feedback during school hours. Aside from classroom tasks, teachers study the curriculum and create effective lesson plans. These overwhelming tasks usually lead teachers to become exhausted and eventually burn out. According to Preechawong et al. (2021), teacher shortage is a big problem in the US and even the world for reasons like exhaustion, student disrespect, and a lack of support from the administration. Due to the high turnover rates and

intimidating nature of the teaching profession, school districts find it increasingly challenging to identify and hire suitable instructors. Given the increasing workload, addressing the challenges of being a teacher and putting in place practical measures to support teachers has become one of the main concerns of the education system worldwide.

Recognizing that teaching is the profession other professions depend on, the US government has initiated several ways to support teachers. According to Darling-Hammond et al. (2023), some of these initiatives are:

- a. Provide more ways for teachers to get higher net compensation through incentives and housing subsidies.

- b. Create programs that will help aspiring teachers access education debt-free, like the "grow-your-own" program.
- c. Mentorship programs are also provided to support their immediate needs, especially for new teachers.
- d. School districts organize professional development to help teachers become experts inside and outside the classroom.

Aside from the listed initiatives above, some districts have also taken steps to respond to this national issue, like hiring teachers from all over the world, providing year-end bonuses, and even changing the school schedule.

Aside from the listed initiatives above, some districts have also taken steps to respond to this national issue, like hiring teachers from all over the world, providing year-end bonuses, and even changing the school schedule. For over a century, the US has followed a 5-day school week schedule and 180 required days per school year. Changing some factors in the school schedule will indeed impact the work morale and well-being of the teachers (Daniels, 2016). There has been an increase of over 600% in the number of districts that follow a four-day school week schedule since 1999 (Four-Day School Week Overview, 2024). One of the reasons for this is to recruit more teachers and achieve a high retention rate. The 4-day work schedule will attract more people to the teaching field.

The four-day school week schedule has gained much popularity among researchers over the past decades, but only a few have focused on its effect on teachers' well-being. This study aims to determine the attitude of public school teachers toward the four-day work schedule and its perceived impact on the teacher's well-being. This research can be a basis for other school districts that still need to follow the new schedule in the education system.

The results of this study helped districts that are not following the 4-day school week schedule assess the effectiveness of this schedule and how it can help improve their teachers' well-being and work morale.

This study's findings will greatly benefit the superintendent and other school district leaders in identifying the advantages and disadvantages of this four-day work schedule and designing strategies that will help accommodate teachers' needs under the new schedule. The results of this study will also help engage teachers during community discussions about the latest schedule. If the survey reveals a positive impact on the well-being of teachers, it will empower them to advocate for this schedule change. Lastly, this study will benefit the community's open discussions that can gather great insights.

1.1. Research Objective

This study aimed to describe teachers' attitude towards the four-day work schedule and provide evidence on how the new schedule impacts teachers' well-being and work morale.

1.2. Theoretical Framework

The following theories related to enhancing teacher's well-being in the workplace were the basis of this study.

Work-life balance, human capital, and educational outcomes theories were the basis of this study. Individuals, in general, strive to achieve a balance between their work and personal responsibilities. This balance is necessary for job satisfaction, performance, and overall well-being. Using human capital theory as a basis for this study, the four-day work schedule demonstrates the school districts' investments in teachers' well-being and work morale. Lastly, based on educational outcomes theory, the new schedule influences teachers' engagement with their role and classroom performance, which can positively impact students' learning experiences.

The foundational framework for this study is the Work-Life Balance Theory, which is significant in a person's well-being. Work-life balance has been a popular theory since the early 1900s, and according to Pillinger (2001), work-life balance is flexible working arrangements that allow employees to avail themselves of working arrangements that

balance work and personal responsibilities. This study identified the effects of the four-day work schedule on teachers' well-being. In addition, the study aimed to know how this schedule change can enhance teachers' work-life and, as a result, affect their job performance and satisfaction.

The main focus of this study is the teachers—the human capital of the education system. Human Capital is the source of value creation for the organization (Wuttaphan, 2017). According to the Human Capital Theory, an individual's well-being is one of the necessary components of human capital. The four-day work schedule can improve the teachers' well-being and increase job satisfaction. Therefore, human capital theory can further support the work-life balance theory and this study.

Teachers' well-being has been proven to affect their effectiveness and educational outcomes (Sutton & Wheatley, 2003). Stress can hinder teachers' achievement of high performance in the classroom and will undoubtedly affect student outcomes. Several factors can lead teachers to be stressed, and one of those is work-life imbalance. Teachers cannot give what they do not have, so if this study proved that teachers' well-being had improved positively because of the schedule change, teachers could provide more care and support to the students and their colleagues.

Figure 1. Theoretical Framework of the Study

2. Methodology

2.1. Research Design

To achieve the objectives of this descriptive quantitative study, which are to describe teachers' attitude towards implementing the four-day work schedule and provide evidence on how the new schedule impacts teachers' well-being and work morale, the following steps were followed: (1) collected data by sending an online questionnaire that had 15 questions to 80 teacher respondents; (2) analyzed data through mean score analysis; and (3) communicated results to St. Joseph School District, which does not follow the four-day work schedule.

2.2. Respondent's Profile

The respondents were teachers from Independence School, a public high school in Missouri. The individual profiles of respondents were not gathered or considered in the data analysis.

2.3. Data Analysis and Techniques

This study used mean score analysis as the data analysis technique. The mean scores for each statement were calculated, and a scale was used to interpret the results. This approach made it possible to categorize mean scores into different levels, helping interpret results and achieve the objectives of this study.

3. Results, Analysis, and Discussion

3.1. Teachers' Attitude Towards the Four-day Work Schedule

The study described the attitude of teachers towards the 4-day school week in conjunction with different teaching areas presented in Table 1.

Table 1
Teachers' Attitude Towards the Four-Day Work Schedule

Statement	Mean	Interpretation
Teachers' perspective on the reasons behind implementing a four-day work schedule.	4.19	Positive
Teachers' perspective on the primary goals or objectives of transitioning to a four-day work schedule.	4.11	Positive
Teachers' initial impression of the four-day work schedule.	3.90	Positive
Perceived effects of the four-day work schedule on teacher-student interactions and relationships.	3.65	Positive
Perceived effects of the four-day work schedule on student engagement within the classroom.	3.49	Neutral
Perceived effects of the four-day work schedule on teachers' flexibility in teaching and curriculum delivery.	4.11	Positive
Perceived effects of the four-day work schedule on opportunities for professional development among teachers.	4.50	Highly Positive

1.00 - 1.49 - Highly Negative
 1.50 - 2.49 - Negative
 2.50 - 3.49 - Neutral
 3.50 - 4.49 - Positive
 4.50 - 5.00 - Highly Positive

Table 1 presents the data gathered regarding teachers' attitude towards the four-day work schedule. It has seven statements that helped achieve objective number 1.

Statements 1 and 2 focused on teachers' perspectives regarding the reasons behind implementing the four-day work schedule and its objectives. The table reports a mean of 4.20 for statement 1 and a mean of 4.10 for statement 2. Statement 3 is about respondents' initial impression of the four-day work schedule and has a mean of 3.90. Table reports a mean of 3.70 for statement 4, which concerns the perceived effects of the 4-day work schedule on teacher-student relationships. Statement 5

concerns the respondents' perception of how the 4DSW will impact student engagement and has a mean of 3.40, as shown in Table 1. Table 1 also reveals a mean of 4.10 for statement 6, which focuses on respondents' perceptions of the 4DSW's effects on teachers' flexibility in teaching and curriculum delivery, and a mean of 4.50 for statement 7, which concerns how teachers expected the new schedule to impact professional development. Lastly, an overall mean of 3.99 is presented in Table 1.

The results were analyzed using mean scores and revealed that teachers have a positive perspective about the reasons behind implementing the four-day work schedule and its objectives. It also showed that teachers have a positive impression of the four-day work schedule but have a neutral stand on how the new schedule will affect student engagement. In addition, it was revealed that teachers have a positive perspective on how the four-day work schedule will affect their teaching flexibility, curriculum delivery, and teacher-student relationships. Lastly, the analysis of results revealed that teachers have a highly positive perspective on how the new schedule will affect professional development opportunities.

The results suggested that teachers expect positive results from implementing the four-day work schedule. Most teachers favor the new schedule because of their positive perspective on how it can affect teaching areas, such as teaching flexibility, curriculum delivery, teacher-student relationships, and professional development. Regarding student engagement, the result suggests that it can be one of the challenging areas when transitioning to the four-day work schedule.

Gathering enough information about the four-day work schedule is essential for the school district's decision-making. Only a few studies have focused on teachers, but most strongly support implementing the four-day work schedule (Turner et al., 2017), consistent with the results gathered from statements one, two, and three. One of the main concerns cited in the study of Turner et al. (2017) is the lesser number of days that students could engage in their learning in school. In addition to that, according to Ordway (2023), since the implementation of the four-day work schedule,

there has been a slight decrease in student engagement due to factors like condensed schedules and the structure of daily schedules, consistent with the results gathered from statement 5. On the other hand, in the study by Marion (2018), teachers said that students were more engaged in the 4DSW because they rested well during the 3-day weekend. In a study by Hanson (2017), one of the top 10 advantages of the four-day work schedule is that it improves student attendance. Students will have an extra day to rest, making them physically ready to return to school and not miss any day since it will be just four days weekly. With that, teachers can establish stronger relationships with them, leading to students' academic improvement. There are fewer student disciplinary referrals, which implies that students are behaving better in the classroom and the student-teacher relationship has improved, supporting the result from statement 4. One of the essential parts of being a teacher is teaching and delivering the curriculum accurately and effectively to the students. The study by Marion (2018) reveals that teachers improved their curriculum delivery because they get an extra day to plan quality activities in the classroom. Surprisingly, the study reveals that teachers have been able to teach the curriculum standards more efficiently since the implementation of the four-day work schedule, which supports the findings of this study. In the area of professional development, the findings of this study are supported by the previous research of Mizell (2010), which reported that teachers have more chances of attending professional development after implementing the 4-day work schedule.

3.2. Effects of the Four-Day Work Schedule on Teachers' Well-Being

As part of the objectives of this study, the effects of the four-day work schedule on different areas of well-being will be assessed in Table 2.

Table 2
Four-Day Work Schedule's Impact on Teachers' Well-Being

Statement	Mean	Interpretation
Physical strain related to teaching duties experienced by teachers since transitioning to a four-day work schedule	4.50	Greatly Improved
Stress levels experienced by teachers since transitioning to a four-day work schedule	4.56	Greatly Improved
Collaboration and teamwork among teachers since transitioning to a four-day work schedule	4.30	Slightly Improved
Teachers' relationships with people outside work since transitioning to a four-day work schedule	4.64	Greatly Improved

1.00 - 1.49 - Greatly Worsened
 1.50 - 2.49 - Slightly Worsened
 2.50 - 3.49 - No change
 3.50 - 4.49 - Slightly Improve
 4.50 - 5.00 - Greatly Improved

Compared to other professions, teachers experience more challenges in their well-being (Walker, n.d.). Teachers' tasks do not end when the bell rings after the last class; they spend time mentoring kids, planning, checking school work, and emailing parents after their contract time. Because of these overwhelming tasks, teachers feel burnt out and eventually lose their drive and leave the profession (Walker, n.d.). Prioritizing teachers' well-being helps retain current teachers and encourages more to join the profession.

A four-day work schedule is one way school districts can improve teachers' well-being. Table 2 has statements 8 to 11, which reveal how the four-day work schedule affects teachers' well-being.

Teachers invest a lot of their time, effort, and strength in educating students and helping them make intelligent decisions in life. Table 2 presents that statement 8, which concerns the perceived effects of the four-day work schedule on teachers' well-being in conjunction with a physical strain related to teaching duties has a mean of 4.50. Statement 9, which concerns the perceived effects of the

four-day work schedule on teachers' well-being in conjunction with stress levels, has a mean of 4.60, as presented in Table 2. The table also presents a mean of 4.30 for statement 10, which concerns the perceived effects of the four-day work schedule on teachers' well-being in conjunction with collaboration and teamwork. Lastly, Table 2 presents statement 11, which concerns the perceived effects of the four-day work schedule on teachers' well-being in conjunction with their relationships outside work, has a mean of 4.60.

The results were analyzed using mean score analysis and revealed that teachers' physical strain related to teaching duties, stress levels, and relationships with people outside of work has greatly improved since implementing the four-day work schedule. It also revealed that teachers' collaboration and teamwork slightly improved after implementing the new schedule.

The results suggested that some factors influencing teachers' duties have changed positively, reducing physical strain and stress levels. The four-day work schedule provides longer time for teachers to rest, which allows them to recharge before going back to work. Extended rest time can also lower stress levels for teachers. The results also suggested that teachers' improved relationships with people outside work can positively affect their overall well-being. Lastly, the results indicated that the four-day work schedule provided teachers with more compressed workdays, allowing them a more structured collaboration opportunity. However, the improvement is slight, therefore the overall impact of the new schedule on collaboration was limited.

Teachers, among all other professionals, are more likely to experience burnout due to many reasons, like workload, student behaviors, curriculum delivery, and lesson planning (Madigan & Kim, 2021). As a result, more teachers miss many days in school, or worse, leave the profession. The four-day work schedule is one of the responses of the education sector to this issue. The findings of this study are supported by the previous research of Doss et al. (2023), which reported that teachers have experienced less burnout since implementing the four-day work schedule, and teachers seldom call in sick because they

are less exhausted under the new schedule. Stress significantly affects one's well-being (Schneiderman et al., 2005). This stress has been one of the reasons why teachers leave the profession. In response, the four-day work schedule was adopted in almost 900 school districts in the US in 2023 (Czachor, 2023). One of the positive effects of the four-day work schedule is that it reduces both student and teacher stress (Morton, 2024), which is consistent with the results of this study. Another factor that affects teacher well-being is positive collegial support and collaboration (Hascher & Waber, 2021). In the four-day work schedule, teachers have more opportunities to collaborate with other teachers (Muir, 2013), which supports the slight improvement in teachers' teamwork and collaboration. Lastly, one of the leading employment issues since 1973 is the work and family time balance (Kossek, 2006). Because of that, institutions find ways to balance working hard and caring for the family. For teachers, this four-day work schedule is one of the school district's responses for teachers to have longer, quality time outside work. According to the study conducted by Marion (2018), one of the best parts of the four-day work schedule is longer family time, especially for teachers who are parents, which supports the results of this study.

3.3. Impacts of the Four-Day Work Schedule on Teachers' Work Morale

The third objective of this study is to assess the four-day work schedule's impact on teachers' work morale, as shown in Table 3. Different factors that contribute to work morale, such as engagement, job satisfaction, workload, and personal life balance, were considered in this assessment.

Table 3
Four-Day Work Schedule's Impact on Teachers' Work Morale

Statement	Mean	Interpretation
Impact of the four-day work schedule on teachers' engagement with their teaching role.	4.14	Positive
Impact of the four-day work schedule on teachers' job satisfaction.	4.18	Positive
Impact of the four-day work schedule on teachers' overall work morale since the implementation.	4.54	Highly Positive
Impact of the four-day work schedule on teachers' ability to balance workload and personal life.	4.38	Positive

- 1.00 - 1.49 - Highly Negative
- 1.50 - 2.49 - Negative
- 2.50 - 3.49 - Neutral
- 3.50 - 4.49 - Positive
- 4.50 - 5.00 - Highly Positive

Teacher morale plays an essential part in the education system; it drives teachers to perform better and provide a more conducive learning environment for our students. With increased teacher work morale problems, a four-day work schedule is one way to respond to it.

Table 3 reports the impact of the four-day work schedule on teachers' work morale. This table has statements 12 to 15 that helped attain objective number 3.

Table 3 presents a mean of 4.14 for statement 12, which concerns the impact of the four-day work schedule on teachers' engagement. Statement 13 concerns the impact of the four-day work schedule on teachers' job satisfaction, and has a mean of 4.18 as presented in Table 3. The table also presents a mean of 4.54 for statement 14, which concerns the impact of the four-day work schedule on teachers' overall work morale when implementing the new schedule. Lastly, the table presents a mean of 4.38 for statement 15, which concerns the impact of the four-day work schedule on teachers' ability to balance workload and personal life.

The results were analyzed using mean score analysis and revealed that the four-day

work schedule positively impacts teachers' engagement with their role, job satisfaction, and ability to balance workload and personal life. The new schedule also has a highly positive impact on teachers' overall work morale.

The results suggested that the four-day work schedule provides an improved work-life balance that motivates teachers to be more enthusiastic about their work. Also, a condensed work schedule can help teachers be more focused and productive during workdays, contributing to job satisfaction. The highly positive impact of the four-day work schedule on teachers' overall work morale suggested that the new schedule is an effective strategy to create a productive work environment and improve teacher morale.

Teacher engagement is essential to students' success and the school district. Enthusiasm and dedication reflect teachers with high work engagement in what they do (Sudibjo & Riantini, 2023). The results of this study are supported by the research of Gower (2017), which reported that there has been a significant improvement in the teaching performance of staff since the implementation of the four-day work schedule. There is a 20% increase in instructional time because of the longer hours they get in every class. Also, the improved engagement of teachers resulted from the frequent professional development that teachers attend during their extra days off. Teachers' job satisfaction and work morale have a positive relationship. Increased job satisfaction improves work morale (Lüleci & Çoruk, 2018). A study by Marion (2016) reveals that most teachers have been satisfied with their work since the four-day week implementation. There is a strong relationship between work motivation and job satisfaction (Bota, 2013), so school districts must take care of this area to avoid issues in the future, like low teacher turnout and teacher attendance problems. The previous studies of Marion (2016) and Bota (2013), support the results of this study as well. Educational outcomes are strongly affected by teacher work morale. Teachers' positive energy in their jobs influences the students' energy (Lüleci & Çoruk, 2018). According to the study by Muir (2013), teachers and students have

become happier since implementing the 4-day school week. This change in the attitude of teachers and students improved the school's morale in general, which is consistent with the results of this study. During the four-day work schedule, teachers achieved a higher sense of enjoyment in coming back to school because they were well-rested. That positive attitude and well-planned lesson plan results in a better student learning experience (Fay, 2019). Teachers invest the most in the student's academic and emotional growth. Teachers can be more effective in this area if they are not exhausted. Many passionate teachers go above and beyond expectations, yet they are still human; they sometimes experience tiredness due to these expectations, highlighting the need for work-life balance (Quintana et al., 2019). Since implementing the four-day work schedule, teachers get more time to rest and work on things outside the teaching profession. One of the benefits of the new schedule is providing more opportunities for teachers to achieve work-life balance (Dantin, 2023), which was confirmed by the results of this study.

4.1 Findings

4.1. Teachers have a positive understanding of the reasons behind implementing the four-day work schedule and its objectives. Their overall initial impression of the four-day work schedule is positive. Specifically, for teacher respondents, a four-day work schedule will positively affect teacher-student relationships and teachers' teaching flexibility and curriculum delivery. They also believe that the new schedule will have a highly positive impact on professional development opportunities. In student engagement, teacher respondents have a neutral stand on how the new schedule will affect it. In general, teachers' attitude towards the four-day work schedule is positive.

4.2. Since implementing the four-day work schedule, teachers have experienced an improvement in their physical strain related to teaching duties and stress levels. In addition, teachers' collaboration and teamwork have

slightly improved, and their relationships with family and friends outside work have significantly improved.

4.3. Since implementing the four-day work schedule, teachers' engagement with their role, job satisfaction, and ability to balance workload and personal life have been positively affected. In addition, the new schedule has a highly positive impact on teachers' work morale.

5. Conclusion

5.1. Teachers' positive attitude towards the four-day work schedule can be explained by their positive perspective on how the new schedule will affect teacher-student relationships, professional development opportunities, teaching, and curriculum delivery. Therefore, adopting the four-day work schedule could be an effective strategy to attract more people to the profession.

5.2. Teachers' overall well-being greatly improved because of the reduced physical strain and stress that the new schedule can offer. Teachers like getting an additional day to rest, spend time with family, attend professional development, and collaborate with other teachers. Therefore, adopting the four-day work schedule was an effective strategy to support educators' well-being.

5.3. This study's findings that the four-day work schedule positively impacts teachers' work morale can be explained by teachers' improved job satisfaction, workload and personal life balance, and engagement with their role. Therefore, implementing the four-day work schedule effectively improved teachers' work morale.

6. Recommendation

6.1. The researcher recommends that school leaders and administrators create plans to smoothly transition teachers to a four-day work schedule and sustain their positive outlook on the new schedule. Further studies must focus on teachers' attitude during the four-day work

schedule. They should investigate how the new schedule changes teachers' attitude about the different teaching areas.

6.2. The researcher recommends that there should be consistent programs centered on stress management and other wellness strategies to improve teachers' well-being. Future studies must focus on the effect of the four-day work schedule on teachers' number of sick leave and absences. They should focus more on how the new schedule affects teachers' physical health.

6.3. The researcher recommends that school district leaders promote and prioritize work-life balance to help teachers manage their responsibilities. Future studies must focus on the impact of the four-day work schedule on teachers' classroom observation ratings and investigate more deeply how the new schedule impacts teachers' performance in the classroom.

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